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Energy efficient driving in dynamic environment

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Future Vehicle Technology

Energy efficient driving in dynamic environment:

Considering other traffic participants and overtaking possibility

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- **Introduction**
- **Problem definition**
- **Optimization method**
- **Initial results**
- **Future plans**

Interdisciplinary Training Network in Multi-Actuated Ground Vehicles (MAGV)

The main target of the ITEAM project is to establish and sustainably maintain the European training network with high grade of interdisciplinarity, which will train strong specialists skilled in research and development of novel technologies in the field of multi-actuated ground vehicles (MAGV)

three research clusters:

- "MAGV integration",
- "Green MAGV",
- "MAGV Driving Environment"

Trainings:

- basic research,
- applied research, and
- experimentations.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 675999

Controller task:

- Plan speed trajectory of a vehicle from point A to point B using the least energy while complying with all constraints and enduring all disturbances

Constraints:

- Traffic lights (V2I, Cloud, Visual sensor)
- Traffic signs (stop sign, speed limits, etc.)
- Road conditions (curvature, low friction, etc.)
- Vehicle constraints (acceleration, power, battery State-of-Charge, etc.)
- Charging or resting time
- Travel time

Disturbances:

- Weather change (temp, air density, etc.)
- Road (slope, slippery road, etc.)
- Traffic (leading vehicle, traffic jam, etc.)

Controller outputs:

- Propulsion torque (Multi-actuated vehicle)
- Human-machine-interface (HMI)
- Steering (automated vehicle)

Controller inputs:

- Vehicle state observers (position, speed, batt SOC, power consumption, etc.)
- Cloud services (Weather conditions, GIS, etc.)
- Environment perception (obstacles, speed limits, traffic lights, etc.)
- Vehicle-to-X communication (V2X)
- Human-machine-interface (HMI)

Challenges:

- Nonlinearity
- Realtime computation vs precision
- Curse of dimensionality
- Dynamic constraints

force balance

$$\dot{s} = v, \tag{1}$$

$$\dot{v} = \frac{F_m(t)}{m} - \frac{F_r}{m}, \tag{2}$$

$$F_r = \frac{1}{2} \rho_a c_d A_f v(t)^2 - c_r mg \cos(\alpha(s(t))) - mg \sin(\alpha(s(t))), \tag{3}$$

$$F_m(t) = \frac{k T_m \eta^{\text{sign}(T_m(t))}}{r_w}, \quad \omega(t) = \frac{kv(t)}{2r_w \pi}. \tag{4}$$

Cost function

$$E_{\min} = \min_{T_m} \int_0^1 (\omega(t) T_m(t) + P_{\text{aux}}) dt. \tag{5}$$

Principle of Optimality

If node J is on the optimal path from node I to node K, then the optimal path from J to K also falls along the same route.

- **Constant speed driving vs Ecodriving**
- **Existing vs proposed overtaking approach**
- **Influence of the road gradient**
- **Influence of the speed difference**

	Energy used [kJ]	difference [%]	Time travelled [s]	time difference [%]
Optimal traj.	213.87	0	59.25	0
speed 9 m/s	231.68	+8.3	58.49	-1.28
speed 11 m/s	237.98	+11.3	49.06	-17.20
speed 7 m/s	237.97	+11.3	73.75	+24.47

Initial results: Existing vs proposed overtaking approach

	Energy used [kJ]	difference [%]	Time travelled [s]	difference [%]
Unconstrained	213.87	0	59.25	0
Constrained	215.45	+ 0.74	57.34	-3.23
LQ deviation	225.15	+ 5.27	58.27	-1.66

- **Implement integration of other constraints into optimization problem (multiple vehicles, vehicles moving in other direction, traffic lights, etc.)**
- **Validate in simulation environment (CarMaker)**
- **Validate in demonstrator vehicle**
- **Integrate predictive thermal management**

virtual vehicle

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